

EASY TEACHING AND LEARNING STRATEGIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL.

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ABSTRACT:

Teaching and learning are crucial part of social life as well as they are not easy matters. In the globalization period, teaching foreign language is becoming essential and it requires strategies in order to make the lessons effective. This article covers some theories by linguists and other scientists about how to teach easily children in primary school, that is, children from 7 to 10 years old, and their learning.

KEY WORDS: teaching methods, strategies, learning styles, game technology, didactic rules.

It is a little difficult to teach a new thing to a child who has just left school. We also know that when we started going to school, each letter or number was taught separately in one lesson every day. Because the ability to keep a lot of new information in the memory of children of this age is not well developed. Gradually, the number of information is increased and thus their acceptance of new information develops. And in this way it will be easy for them to accept. Teachers pass the lessons accordingly, and if the children do not master the lesson well, they pass it again.

There are different ways to teach elementary school children. For example, when teaching each letter, giving examples of words that begin with that letter or teaching it with poems will help the child remember it. Therefore, the lesson will be interesting. In addition, various merit-based games are used to check the level of mastery of the lesson. It would not be wrong to say that this method is the best and tested method of returning a new topic that was covered in the last lesson. There are many similar methods and all of them are effective in their own way. If teachers use these during the lesson and students actively participate in these methods, it will be beneficial for both parties.

Game technology:

They allow elementary school students to develop all kinds of universal activities:

- the rules of behavior and roles in the group have been mastered;
- the possibilities of the groups are considered;
- will acquire the skills of joint collective activity, the individual characteristics of students necessary to achieve the specified game goals will be developed;
- cultural traditions are collected and introduced into the game by participants, teachers, additional tools
- is involved with visual aids, textbooks, computer technologies, etc

These help children to work in a group, behave in a group and develop similar characteristics. In addition, the use of various visual aids or similar methods in lessons develops the child's ability to remember and increases the child's interest in the lesson.

M.A. Rybnikova cites 4 didactic rules as the basis of the methodology:

1. Education should be of a character that affects the understanding of students in every way.
2. Pupils clearly understand the issue before them.
3. The methodist should have the ability to show new complex phenomena as easily as familiar ones.
4. Connecting deduction with induction.

M.A. Rybnikova views this methodological system as a live process and emphasizes that the main focus should be on the methodological system. These views require a new approach to the analysis and interpretation of literary and artistic works organized in primary school reading classes. Conducting the analysis of the work on the basis of step-by-step consistency allows to direct the educational activities of students to a specific goal.

K. D. Ushinsky studied education in foreign schools and wrote his work "Primary Education Methodology". In it, the creation of rules, laws, procedures, methods and tools made a significant contribution to the didactics science. In his opinion, every subject should be taught according to the age and strength of the student, and he emphasizes the need to engage in physical work in order to rest from mental work. The idea of nationalism of education is the main idea in Ushinsky's pedagogical theory. He emphasizes that education is fundamental and decisive in the work of education and training, that education subjugates education, but does not bring out its unique essence. Ushinsky's teaching process used the principles of demonstration, awareness, thoroughness, conformity to children's strengths and consistency of education.

In general, Ushinsky made the idea of nationalism of education the basis of the theory of education, developed the foundations and methodology of primary education, which is one of his great contributions to the development of pedagogy. Today, many pedagogues are effectively using the researches and achievements of Ushinsky and other similar scientists in their classes.

In conclusion, children should be given a good education from the beginning. The best way to do this is to use different methods.

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